

Factors Influenced Medical Specialization Choices Among Medical Registrars at Ibrahim-Malik Teaching Hospital, 2023.

Marafi Ahmed, Noura Hashim

Abstract

Background: Choosing a medical specialty is a complex process influenced by various factors, which can help ensure an equitable distribution of physicians that meet the country's healthcare demands. Additionally, insights into these factors can assist medical students and young doctors in receiving guidance and advice that align with their aspirations, hopes, and healthcare needs.

Goals: Evaluate factors influenced specialty choice among medical registrars.

Estimating time of choosing a medical specialty. Determine the level of satisfaction of the registrars with their current career.

Method and Materials: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Ibrahim-Malik Teaching Hospital to know the factors influenced medical registrars' choice of specialization. By self-administered questionnaire, a total of 130 registrars were included in the study.

Results: Out of 192 registrars from different disciplines, 130 responded to the survey (53.6% female, 46.4% male). Major factors affected specialty selection included personal interest (51.4%), experience in the specialty (31.9%), specialty content (31.8%), mentor influence (29.7%), variety of patients (27.5%), and future job opportunities (26.8%). The study revealed that 33.3% of registrars choose their specialty after completing houseman training, while 26.1% made the decision during houseman training, and 26.1% during medical school. The remaining 14.5% made their choice after graduation. Regarding satisfaction, 58.7% of registrars were satisfied, 39.1% were very satisfied, and 2.2% expressed dissatisfaction.

Conclusion: The specialty choice of registrars at Ibrahim-Malik Teaching Hospital was influenced by various factors, with personal interest, experience in the specialty, and specialty content being the key drivers. Most registrars decided on their specialty after houseman training, and overall, they expressed high satisfaction. These concerns should be emphasized by the relevant authorities.

Key Word: Registrars, Specialty, Career Satisfaction, Factors, Choice.

INTRODUCTION

Medical specialties are specific branches of medical practice that focus on particular patient groups, diseases, skills, or philosophies. Registrars, who are doctors in the middle of their training, play a crucial role in patient care, working long shifts and gaining experience. Specialization in medicine offers several benefits, such as increased patient volume, improved efficiency, and reduced errors. However, there is a persistent shortage and unequal distribution of medical specialists in developing nations, which

impacts access to quality healthcare. Understanding the factors influencing specialty selection is vital for addressing workforce needs and providing adequate training opportunities. Many doctors struggle to choose the right specialty, considering various factors such as personal interests, background, clinical experiences, training duration, and financial and lifestyle considerations. The decision-making process varies among individuals, with some deciding before medical school and others exploring

multiple options before settling on a specialization. Despite its significance, little research has been conducted to compare the relative importance of different criteria in specialty choice. Therefore, our study aims to identify and evaluate the various factors influencing specialty selection.

Method and Materials

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design and was conducted at Ibrahim Malik Teaching Hospital, situated on Africa St, Khartoum state, Sudan. Ibrahim Malik Hospital is a government-owned facility established in 1977 AD, serving as a general central teaching hospital. All registrars present at the hospital during the study period were included in the research sample. The study sample consisted of a total of 130 registrars.

Data collection was performed through the utilization of a self-administered questionnaire. Participation in the study was voluntary, ensuring that individuals willingly chose to take part. The collected data were subsequently analyzed using SPSS version 26, a statistical software package. The analysis involved the generation of tables and figures to present the findings in a structured and visual format.

RESULTS

The research was conducted on a sample of 130 registrars from various disciplines. The results indicate the distribution of respondents based on gender, with females accounting for 53.6% and males for 46.4% of the total participants (N=130). In terms of age group, the most prevalent category was individuals aged 20-29, comprising 60.9% of the sample (N=130). Furthermore, the study examined whether the registrars had family members working in healthcare professions. The findings revealed that 70.3% of the registrars had family members who were health professionals. The nature of the relationship between the registrars and their

family members was also explored. The most common relationship was with a sister (21.9%), followed by equal proportions for father and mother (20%). Conversely, the least common relationships were with a wife (1%) and a sibling (2.9%). Regarding the specific healthcare professions of the registrars' family members, the majority were doctors, accounting for 53.3% of the cases. Pharmacists represented 14.3% of the total, followed by laboratory scientists (13.3%), dentists (10.5%), and nurses (8.6%). For a detailed breakdown of the medical registrars' specialties, please refer to Table 1.

Table 1: Shows medical registrar specialty: -

	Frequency	Percent
Anesthesiology	16	11.6
Emergency medicine	17	12.3
Internal medicine	21	15.2
Obstetrics/Gynecology	21	15.2
Orthopedic	19	13.8
Pediatric surgery	7	5.1
Pediatrics	18	13.0
Surgery	17	12.3
Urology	2	1.4
Total	138	100.0

The research findings indicate that among the registrars surveyed, 44.9% were in their first year of specialty. Additionally, 16.7% of registrars were in their second or fourth year, 12.3% were in their third year, and 9.4% were in their fifth year. Furthermore, the study examined the factors that influenced the choice of medical specialty among the registrars. These factors and their corresponding details can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: Shows the factors that influenced medical registrars' specialty choice in percentage and degree:-

	No Influencing	Little influencing	Influencing	Very influencing
Personal Interests	5.8 (8)	15.9 (22)	26.8 (36)	51.4 (71)
Gender role	39.8(55)	31.1(43)	15.9 (22)	13.2 (18)
Financial/income expectations	31.1 (43)	29.7 (41)	16.7 (23)	22.5 (31)
Work/life balance	23.2 (32)	28.2 (39)	30.4 (42)	18.1 (25)
Future job opportunities in that field	15.2 (21)	16.7 (23)	41.3 (57)	26.8 (37)
Duration of the rotation	34.8 (48)	26.1 (36)	25.4 (35)	13.8 (19)
training availability	21.0 (29)	21.0 (29)	34.1 (47)	23.9 (33)
Specialty content	13.8 (19)	14.5 (20)	39.9 (55)	31.8 (44)
Competitiveness of the specialty	23.8 (33)	22.5 (31)	34.1 (47)	19.6 (27)
Expectations of family	42.0 (58)	23.2 (32)	16.7 (23)	18.1 (25)
Direct interaction with patients	22.5 (31)	22.5 (31)	31.9 (44)	23.2 (32)
Specialty Prestige	30.5 (42)	23.9 (33)	26.8 (37)	18.8 (26)
Personal experience in the specialty	23.2 (32)	15.9 (22)	29.0 (40)	31.9 (44)
Variety of patients	20.3 (28)	22.5 (31)	29.7 (41)	27.5 (38)
Mentor influences	28.3 (39)	21.0 (29)	29.7 (42)	29.7 (42)
Geographical location	37.0 (51)	21.7 (30)	26.1 (36)	15.2 (21)

while Table 3 presents the time periods during which the registrars made their specialty choices.

Table 3: Shows the time when the medical registrars choose their Specialty.

	Frequency	Percent
At houseman training	36	26.1
At medical school	36	26.1
Period after graduation	20	14.5
Period after houseman	46	33.3
Total	138	100.0

We revealed that the majority of registrars, specifically 61.6%, do not consider shifting their specialty. Furthermore, 56.6% of the registrars reported that the factors influencing their decision-making process had changed. Interestingly, Figure 1 indicates that a significant proportion of these registrars expressed satisfaction with their current situation.

figure 1: Shows the medical registrar's degree of satisfaction: -

Discussion

The selection of a medical specialization holds paramount importance in a doctor's professional career, impacting both personal fulfillment and society at large. Given the gravity of this decision and its ramifications, numerous complexities and factors come into play, influencing its outcome. This research aims to provide insights into the factors that influenced medical specialization choices among registrars at Ibrahim Malik Teaching

Hospital during the period of December 2022-2023. A total of 130 registrars from various specialties participated in the study, with the majority of them (15.2%) belonging to the internal medicine and obstetrics and gynecology disciplines. Among the registrars, a significant portion (53.6%) were females, while 60.9% fell into the age group of 20-29. Additionally, a considerable number (44.9%) were in their first year of specialization. Notably, 70.3% of the registrars reported having a family member who worked in the healthcare profession. Among these, 53.3% were doctors themselves, with fathers (20%), mothers (20%), sisters (21.9%), and brothers (15.2%) being the most common relatives. The study shed light on multiple factors that influenced the choice of medical specialization, with participants rating these factors on a scale ranging from "very influencing," "influencing," "little influencing," to "no influencing." The factors perceived as "very influencing" included personal interests (51.4%), gender role (13.2%), financial/income expectations (22.5%), work/life balance (18.1%), future job opportunities in the field (26.8%), duration of the rotation (13.8%), training availability (23.9%), specialty content (31.8%), competitiveness of the specialty (19.6%), expectations of the family (18.1%), direct interaction with patients (23.2%), specialty prestige (18.8%), personal experience in the specialty (31.9%), variety of patients (27.5%), mentor influences (29.7%), and geographical location (15.2%). These findings closely align with a study conducted at Aga Khan University Hospital, where residents from internal medicine and different sub-specialties reported factors such as a variety of medical problems, academic experience, autonomy potential, and role models as the primary influencers, with financial reasons and family influence playing relatively lesser roles [1]. Additionally, the study revealed that a significant proportion of registrars (33.6%) made their specialization choice after completing their Houseman training, while a smaller percentage (26.1%)

made their decision during their Houseman training or medical school. This observation is logical as doctors can better assess their skills and inclinations after being exposed to real-world work environments. A study conducted in Southeastern Nigeria supports this notion, revealing that the majority of participants (97.2%) had decided on their specialty choice by the end of their fifth postgraduate year. It also highlighted that women tended to choose a specialist career earlier, either during medical school or before completing their postgraduate training [2]. Similarly, a study conducted in Mangalore, India, demonstrated that many participants made their decision during the final year of medical school or during their internship. By the age of 23, 130 participants had already chosen their specialty. This differs from studies conducted in other countries, where 37% made their specialty choice within the first year following graduation, and 43% decided by the second or third year after graduation [3]. Furthermore, it was found that 53 (38.4%) of the registrars had considered a specialty shift at some point. Among those, a majority of 30 (56.6%) revealed that their influencing factors had undergone changes. This ratio was higher than expected, suggesting that as doctors progress through different stages, their perspectives evolve, leading to a shift in the factors that hold significance in their professional lives. Despite this, the overall findings of the study indicated that 81 (58.7%) of the registrars expressed satisfaction with their chosen specialty. Similar to our study, a research conducted at King Saud University and King Saud University Medical City in Saudi Arabia, involving 353 residents, revealed that nearly half of the participants were satisfied with their residency program, with 24.1% reporting high levels of satisfaction [4].

Conclusion

The research findings at Ibrahim Malik Teaching Hospital provide several important conclusions:

1. The primary factors that significantly influenced the choice of specialty among the registrars were "personal interest, personal experience in the specialty, specialty content, and mentor influence." Conversely, factors such as "expectations of the family, gender role, geographical location, and duration of the rotation" had relatively lesser influence.
2. A significant majority of the registrars made their specialty choice after completing their houseman training. This suggests that exposure to real-world work environments and practical experience played a crucial role in their decision-making process.
3. The study revealed that the majority of the registrars expressed satisfaction with their chosen specialty. Additionally, less than half of them considered a potential specialty shift, indicating a relatively stable career path among the participants.

Limitations

We encountered several limitations during the course of this research including the convenience sampling methods it may introduce bias into our data collection process, as it relies on selecting participants who are readily available and accessible. Also, the ethical considerations: Our data collection was subject to ethical considerations and constraints imposed by the hospital setting. Additionally, collaboration of hospital staff and availability and permission of registrars as the participation of registrars in our research depended on their availability and willingness to take part during the data collection period. This could have introduced a selection bias, as those who chose to participate may differ in certain characteristics from those who did not, potentially influencing the results. It is important to consider these limitations when interpreting the findings of our study.

Acknowledgment

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to all those who have supported and guided us during our study, providing us with the necessary strength and knowledge to accomplish this research.

References

- 1-Factors Affecting the Choice of Sub-specialty among Medical Residents. Rohama Samar , Syed Ahsan Ali , Victoria Samar , Sara Samar , Sajjad Ali Khan , Summaira Mansoor.
- 2-Factors Influencing the Career Choices of Medical Graduates February 2012 Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research . Smitha Bhat.
- 3-Factors influencing junior doctors' choices of future specialty: trends over time and demographics based on results from UK national surveys. Fay Smith, Trevor W Lambert, and Michael J Goldacre .
- 4- Factors Influencing Choice of Medical Specialty of Pre Residency Medical Graduates in Southeastern Nigeria . Boniface Ikenna Eze, Onochie Ike Okoye, Ferdinand Chinedu Maduka- Okafor, Emmanuel Nwabueze Aguwa.

